

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEES JOB SATISFACTION AT AMARJOTHI TEXTILES LTD., SAMALAPURAM, TIRUPUR

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Abstract:

Human Resources in an organization play significant role in contributing to organizational effectiveness. Human resources are the wealth of an organization. Human Resource management is concerned with the human being in an organization. It reflects a new outlook which views organization man power and its resources and assets. Human resource is the knowledge, abilities, skills, talents and aptitude of an organization work force. The Study aims at discovering the level of job satisfaction of employees in Amarjothi Textiles in Samalapuram. With the help of the study the management can take effective measures to increase the level of job satisfaction by concentrating on the significant factor. Through this management can inverse the overall performance of the employees. The success of an organization depends upon the ability of its employees. This study was untested to know the level of satisfaction of worker. It helps to identify the problem of the workers and solution to the problem. This study gains importance in recertifying the problem by giving some suggestions and recommendation. From the detailed analysis made by the researcher it is inferred that the maximum employees of Amarjothi Textiles Ltd are highly satisfied with the existing system of administration, payment system, evaluation system, superior subordinate relationship, managerial hierarchy and job security. It can be concluded that the employees job satisfaction is considered as good at Amarjothi Textiles Ltd.

Keywords: organizational effectiveness, Amarjothi Textiles, job satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Human Resources in an organization play significant role in contributing to organizational effectiveness. Human resources are the wealth of an organization. Human Resource management is concerned with the human being in an organization. It reflects a new outlook which views organization man power and its resources and assets. Human resource is the knowledge, abilities, skills, talents and aptitude of an organization work force.

Job satisfaction means positive attitude or feeling towards one's job. An individual may hold different attitude towards various aspects of job characteristic of individual also it influence job satisfaction individuals with positive affinity are more likely to be satisfied with their job than individuals with negative affinity.

The Indian textile industry has its roots going back several thousand years. After the industrial revolution in Europe, this sector in India also saw its growth of an industrial complex. The size of our Indian textile industry is estimated Rs 1, 24,000 crores constituting seven percent of the GDP. The industry has fair global exposures textile exports constitute about 35 % of the total foreign exchange earnings of the country. One of the company actively participating in the textile industry is Amarjothi Textiles Ltd which is selected for the present study.

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STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The Study aims at discovering the level of job satisfaction of employees in Amarjothi Textiles in Samalapuram. With the help of the study the management can take effective measures to increase the level of job satisfaction by concentrating on the significant factor. Through this management can inverse the overall performance of the employees. The success of an organization depends upon the ability of its employees. This study was untested to know the level of satisfaction of worker. It helps to identify the problem of the workers and solution to the problem. This study gains importance in recertifying the problem by giving some suggestions and recommendation.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the employee job satisfaction towards their job at Amarjothi Textiles ltd.
2. To find out the satisfaction level towards working conditions and welfare Facilities provided by the company
3. To suggest some measures to the management in satisfying their employees towards their job.

METHODOLOGY

Source of Data

Primary data were collected through the survey method by using questionnaire mode.

Sample Size

The total sample size of the study was confined to 75 respondents those are the employees of the company.

Sample Method.

Random sampling method was used to select the respondents.

Statistical Tools

Percentage analyses were used to analyze the data.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The limitations of the study were.

1. Due to lack of time the collection of data from the employees are restricted to 75
2. During the data collection from the employees some of the employees do not co-operate they hesitate to disclose the truth.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rengachari N.R., in his study “A study on job satisfaction of employees in Handloom weavers Co-operative societies,” has examined the extent of satisfaction or dissatisfaction on job factors as perceived by workers. He found that highest age group of workers have more satisfaction that the young age employees so also the workers with low education have more income of the worker increase, his satisfaction also increases. The researcher also found that training and experience develop the level of satisfaction of the workers while there is no significant

relationship between number of dependents and satisfaction of the workers. Working condition and managerial attitude are the major dissatisfies to the workers in the cooperative societies.”

Geetha N.in her study ‘‘ Job Satisfaction – A comparative study of men and women executives in banking sectors, has attempted to find out the level of satisfaction among bank find out that satisfies for men executive are the pay scales, promotion opportunity, recognition, better organizational climate and status. While the satisfies for female executives are the better organizational image, conductive working environment, posting in major metropolitan cities, high pay, Scale and job security, The Chi-square analysis revealed that the background variables such as sex, age education, working atmosphere, income marital status and occupational status influence the level of satisfaction. The research concludes that there exists a significant relationship between background variables and job satisfaction.’’

Mr. Rajiv in his study.” A Study of Job Satisfaction of supervisors Job Satisfaction is an attitudinal variable that can be a diagnostic indicator of how a person is doing in one of the major domains of his or her life. He found that Job satisfaction is more in old age people where younger people shows are some dissatisfaction due to high qualification and salary. According to supervisor’s words. Job Satisfaction will be increased more only through personal Development and training Programs kept by the Organization. Age and Education is the main [problem that shows the dissatisfaction by the supervisors. Organization can do much to help in this area by doing things to enhance Job Satisfaction.

PROFILE OF AMARJOTHI TEXTILES

Amarjothi textile is incorporated in the year 1990. The textile is situated at samalapuram. This is located 40kilometers from the heart of the Coimbatore city. The main process undertaken by the textiles is the purchase of raw cotton and processing into cloth. The raw material is purchased from local as well as from other states. The processing time to convert cotton into yarn is approximately one week. Then the yarn is used to weave cloths. Cloth is absolute essential basic need of every human being the market from the finished goods will exist so long the human being exist and increase in proportions with the increase in population. Mr.Surendar is the board of director and Mr.Raju is the manager of the textile. It is sole trader textile. Total number of employees in the concern is 324 they are working in shift basis. Cloth is marketed through the brokers and consignment agents. A cloth is also exported to Bangladesh.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The collected data through the questionnaire are tabulated and presented in the following table. Percentage analysis is used to draw inference from the tabulated data.

Level of satisfaction of employees at Amarjothi Textiles Ltd

S.No.	Particulars	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neither satisfied (nor) dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied
1	Satisfaction with their current Job	19	46	6	4	-
2	Agree that they are placed at right Job	25	40	7	3	-
3	Payment of Salary at the right time	40	25	10	-	-

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4	Training and Development program	20	35	8	5	2
5	Promotional Policy	20	39	7	6	3
6	Health and Welfare facilities					
7	Welfare Facilities	20	30	14	11	-
8	Approach of the Superiors	15	25	33	2	-
9	Relationship among Colleagues	18	35	12	10	-
10	Superior motivates to finish the task on time	18	32	15	10	-
11	Hierarchical Communication System	15	35	10	15	-
12	Leave facilities and Fringe benefits	12	45	18	18	-

From the above table it is understood that majority 61.3% of the respondents are satisfied with their current job. Minority 5% of respondents are dissatisfied with the current job. 53.3% of the respondents agree that they are placed at the right job. Minority 9.3% of respondents are neither agree nor disagree that they are placed at right job.

It is inferred that 93.3% of the respondents are getting salary at right time. 6.7% of the respondents are not getting their salary at right time.

Among the respondents, 46.7% of the respondents are satisfied with training and development program of the company and 2.7% of respondents are dissatisfied with the same. It is understood that 26.7% of the respondents are strongly agree with the promotional policy.

Majority 60% of the respondents are satisfied with the health and wealth facilities. Minority 40% of respondents are not satisfied with the health and wealth conditions provided by the company.

As far as welfare facilities are concerned 26.7% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 40% of the respondents are satisfied, 18.7% of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied and 14.6% of the respondents are dissatisfied. 44% of the respondents are having good relationship with superior. Minority 2.7% of respondents are not having good relationship with the superior. 67 % of the people are satisfied with the motivational factors of this company whereas 23% are not satisfied with the same.

Majority 66.7% of the respondents said that the company helped for career and personal development. Minority 13.3% of respondents said that the company not helps in their career and personal development.

From the above table it is understood that 20% of the respondents are highly participated in organisation growth. 66.7% of the respondents are medium participated. 13.3% of the respondents are not participated in the Organisational growth.

From the above table it is considered that 20% of the respondents are highly satisfied with hierarchical communication system. 46.7%of the respondents are satisfied. 13.3%of the Respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. 20% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the hierarchical communication system

From the above table it is clear that 13.3% of the respondents are strongly agreed with the grievance handling 46.7%of the respondents are agreeing. 20% of the respondents are neither agreed nor disagree. 20% of the respondents are disagreeing with their grievance handling properly.

Majority 66.7% of the respondents said that the management accepting their suggestion. Minority 33.3% of respondents said that the management is not accepting their suggestions.

From the above table it is understood that 16% of the respondents are highly satisfied. 60% of the respondents are satisfied .24% of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. 24% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the leave facilities fringe benefits.

Majority 60% of the respondents are satisfied with the leave facilities and fringe benefits. Minority 16% of respondents are highly satisfied with the leave facilities and fringe benefits. From the above table it is understood that 80% of the respondents are having job security 20% of the respondents are does not having job security in Amarjothi textiles.

From the above table it is understood that 82.7% of the respondents are getting timely feedback regarding performance on evaluation by the superior and 17.3% of the respondents are not getting timely feedback regarding performance evaluation by the superior.

FINDINGS

From the detailed analysis made by the researcher it is inferred that the maximum employees of Amarjothi Textiles Ltd are highly satisfied with the existing system of administration, payment system, evaluation system, superior subordinate relationship, managerial hierarchy and job security. It can be concluded that the employees job satisfaction is considered as good at Amarjothi Textiles Ltd.

SUGESTION

1. The company may still improve their welfare facility.
2. The company may improve the relationship with colleague to complete the task on time.
3. The management may improve their communication with their subordinates for better coordination of different departments in organization.

CONCLUSION

Employees are the integral part of the organization. Without employees' satisfaction the organization places its survival at risk. Job satisfaction is one of the important factors which affect the efficiency and effectiveness of the organizations employees is satisfied when their expectation from the work and the reward equalized. The study analyzed some specific area like superior and subordinate relationship working condition health facility, welfare facility etc. Small percentage of the workers are not satisfied in their working condition. If the manager or superiors recognize the performances of the workers they are motivated to work. An appreciation from superiors for better performance is an incentive to the employees work the improvement in welfare measures will definitely lead to better efficiency among employees and there by leading to better performance growth of Amarjothi Textiles Ltd.

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